

NDAC/LO/009

1982 Oct 19

ERRATA (2):

WP3100: Preprocessing of IDT Data (Definition)

(NDAC/LO/005)

The attached three pages should replace the original pp 6, 8, and 13 in NDAC/LO/005.

The revisions concern:

- p 6 - a redefinition of the signal phase ($\hat{\beta}_3$) to make it independent of the a priori stellar position and attitude;
- p 8 - adding multiplicity information as input from the star catalogue (DID10); and
- p 13 - adding magnitude, colour, and multiplicity as output to the IDT signal catalogue (DID15).

square-root information formalism is adopted, the output would be the data equations $(\underline{\Phi}^{\frac{1}{2}}, \underline{\Phi}^{\frac{1}{2}}\hat{\underline{\beta}})$, where $\underline{\Phi}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is the upper-triangular Cholesky factor. A priori data, $(\underline{G}^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \underline{G}^{-\frac{1}{2}}\underline{\beta})$, are then incorporated by means of the Partial Triangularization algorithm (Annex A, Appendix C) instead of the analytically equivalent (A.10.14). It may be noted that a different indexing of the signal parameters may then be advantageous: e.g. β_5 should be the most frequently needed parameter [probably the signal phase, β_3 in (1)], since its solution from the data equations requires the least number of operations (one division).

The estimated phase $\hat{\beta}_3$ depends on the assumed stellar position, attitude, etc through the reference grid coordinates. This dependency should be removed by modifying, before output, as below:

$$\hat{\beta}_3 := \hat{\beta}_3 + 2\pi.\text{frac}(\tilde{G}_K^*) \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{G}_K^*$ is the smoothed reference grid coordinate at mid-frame.

3.4. Output

The main output of the IDT Preprocessing consists of the signal parameters with covariances etc, which are stored chronologically on the IDT Signal Catalogue.

For stars whose data in the Star (Input) Catalogue satisfy certain criteria (e.g. brightness, non-multiplicity, known B-V), the estimated parameters $\beta_4 = (M_2/M_1)\cos(v_2)$ and $\beta_5 = (M_2/M_1)\sin(v_2)$ are stored on a separate file together with their covariance, the star identification number, time of observation (TMID), mean field coordinates $(\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}, f)$, and colour (B-V). This file is later processed into a 'calibration table' from which a priori values of $(M_2/M_1)\cos(v_2)$ and $(M_2/M_1)\sin(v_2)$ can be computed as functions of time, field coordinates, and B-V. These values are needed with the Location Estimator to obtain improved signal phases and for the detection of multiple stars.

For the photometry, and also in order to monitor the instrument e.g. with respect to the focus, it is also desirable to estimate and output M_1 . This can be done directly for very bright stars for which the background is negligible; otherwise it will be necessary to estimate also the background by comparing stars of different brightness. The procedure for this remains TBD, but we assume that the OTF output will consist of the three parameters $M_1, (M_2/M_1)\cos(v_2), (M_2/M_1)\sin(v_2)$ [= OTF(K), K=1,3] and covariances.

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	RANGE			NUM ACC		DIG-ITS
				MIN	MAX	DEF	ABS	REL	
DID 10 (rev. 1)	OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE INPUT TO : IDT PREPROCESSING PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.10.19								
ID	-	1.1. <u>For each star in frame:</u> object identification number	-	0	$9 \cdot 10^8$	0	1	-	8
RA $\emptyset$	$\alpha_{\odot}$ (p4)	Right Ascension at TEPOCH	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12
DEC $\emptyset$	$\delta_{\odot}$ (p4)	Declination at TEPOCH	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-11}	-	12
PMRA	$\mu_{\alpha} \cos \delta_{\odot}$ (p4)	Proper Motion in R.A. at TEPOCH (times $\cos \delta_{\odot}$)	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19}	-	9
PMDEC	μ_{δ} (p4)	Proper Motion in Dec. at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19}	-	9
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	trigonometric parallax	rad	$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0	10^{-11}	-	6
BMAG	-	blue (B) magnitude	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	-	4
BMV	-	colour index B-V	mag	-1	3	99	10^{-2}	-	4
SDBMV	-	standard deviation of BMV	mag	0	3	99	10^{-2}	-	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	-	4

DESIGNATION	OUTPUT FROM : IDT PREPROCESSING		INPUT TO : IDT SIGNAL CATALOGUE		PAGE : 1 OF 1		DATE : 82.10.19		
	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	DIG-ITS REL	
IFRAME	-	1. For each frame: frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_k (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
NSTAR	-	number of objects in frame	-	0	10	0	1	-	2
ID	-	1.1. For I=1, NSTAR: object identification number	-	0	10^8	0	1	-	8
BMAG, BMV, SDBMV	-	magnitude, colour, s.d. of colour	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	-	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	-	4
IFIELD	$(-1)^f$ (p8)	field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
ETAA, ZETAA	$\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}$ (p32)	approximate field coordinates	rad	$-9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	10^{-7}	-	5
NACC, NREJ	-	no. of samples accepted/rejected	-	0	9000	0	1	-	4
GOF	-	goodness-of-fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
BETA(K), K=1,5	$\hat{\beta}$ (p29)	estimated signal parameters	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6
CBETA(K,L), K=1,5, L=K,5	Φ^{-1} (p29)	covariance of BETA(K) (or equivalent)	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	-	10^{-6}	6